

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/353463114>

Operation of Time and Cost Estimation of Road and Bridge Projects

Article · July 2021

CITATIONS

0

READS

76

4 authors, including:

[Er.Khem Raj Joshi](#)

6 PUBLICATIONS 4 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

[Anjay kumar Mishra](#)

Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy Nepal and Madan Bhandari Technological Univ...

284 PUBLICATIONS 832 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Some of the authors of this publication are also working on these related projects:

Risk and Safety [View project](#)

Risk and Safety [View project](#)

Operation of Time and Cost Estimation of Road and Bridge Projects

Er. Khem Raj Joshi

Registrar, Nepal Engineering Council, Kathmandu, Nepal

Email; khemjoshi2000@gmail.com

Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra

Associate Professor and Research Director

Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy Nepal, Pokhara University Uurlabari 3, Morang

OrcidID:0000-0003-2803-4918;Email: anjaymishra2000@gmail.com

Prof. Dr. Rabindra Nath Shrestha

Faculty in Department of Civil Engineering

Tribhuvan-University,Pulchowk Campus

Email; rabindra@ioe.edu.np

Dr. Tarumay Ghoshal

Associate Dean R & C

Faculty in Department of Civil Engineering .DIT-University

Email; tarumay.ghoshal@dituniversity.edu.in

Abstract

The construction industry for Roads and Bridges in Nepal is in a transitional phase where the new technologies are recently introduced but not everyone is in access of it. The methods of works also greatly vary on the individual capacity of each contractor. So, a practical approach is necessary for developing a methodology for contract estimation. With frequent change in regulations regarding extension of time, the need for the accuracy and precision in the estimation of contract duration has even increased more.

This paper aims at developing empirical formulae to identify the relation between contract duration and the contract cost based on the data of roads and bridges completed within the last five years. A total of 83 bridges and 78 road projects were analyzed to determine a relation between the cost and the time period for these projects. Equations Where, T= duration of work in days.

C= Cost of the project measured in lakhs was obtained For Bridges:-

$$T = 111.018C^{0.215}$$

For Roads:-

$$T = 92.482C^{0.2159}$$

Time cost model is a simple yet effective way to deal with the uncertainties that comes in the procurement processes in the estimation of construction duration. This model can easily be reconstructed with new dates along the span of time. With changes in technologies and work culture, the time required for the prediction of construction duration also changes. With this model, and with proper data on construction duration and cost, the time cost model can be regenerated.

Keywords; Duration of Contract, Estimation, Road, Bridge, Cost of Contract

Introduction

Public tendering on construction in Nepal is governed by “Public Procurement Act 2007 (PPA) and Public Procurement Regulation 2007” (PPR) in Nepal. There is provision of “duration to be mentioned while preparing the cost estimate” in rule 9 of the Regulation but this provision does not state the methods of determining the construction contract duration (CCD). Also, in the last one year there have been more than four amendments in the PPR and one amendment on PPA has already been passed from the cabinet. Each of these amendments have included the topic of Extension of time for construction duration. The provisions for EOT have been changing as if the nation is following a trial and error policy for EOT. With so much attention and experimentation on the EOT, little has been mentioned and formulated for the estimation of contract duration. As the provisions of EOT can't be applied well without a discrete methodology for contract duration. Project Duration signifies the success or failure of stipulated project.

The estimation of appropriate contract duration is also an essential tool for fairly bringing in action the provisions in bid-doc like Liquidated Damage and bonuses. Many adjudication and arbitration cases have been registered as a result of un-satisfied parties regarding the Liquidated damage and bonus provision (Ghimire and Mishra,2029). When the contract duration is estimated in the planning phase with greater accuracy, satisfying both the client and contractor, it is likely that such disputes can be easily avoided. Also, the client can enforce the bonus provision with greater confidence. Mishra (2019) conducted extensive research and validated Brownmillow time and cost model for the bridge construction projects of Nepal. The result of his research was on Brownmillow's Time Cost (BTC) Model stated that the time and cost factors of the BTC model can be influenced and fluctuated at different levels by various factors, for example, the sort of venture, the atmosphere states of the area where the undertaking is understood, the adjustments in the conversion standard, and the particulars of the agreement based on study of public health building (Mishra et al, 2020).

The objective of Research

The paper aims to establish time and cost operational relation for road and bridge projects to develop empirical formulae.

Literature Review

Bromilow's Time Cost (BTC) Model

Hence, the model proposed by Bromilow has been concentrated by various specialists at various pieces of the world, particularly considering the impact of nearby factors (Savas Bayram, 2017). Albeit a few new methodologies, for example, utilizing Artificial Neural Networks (Petruseva, Pusic, & Pancovska, 2016) reference group class (Savas Bayram & Al-Jibouri, 2018), genetic algorithms (Haque, Hasin, & Akhtar, 2012) etc., proposed for foreseeing time cost relationship in development projects, the BTC approach actually is the generally acknowledged methodology because of its effortlessness.

Task fruition time is frequently utilized as a marker of contractor's, productivity, polished skill and capability which mirrors the capacity of a project worker to put together and control site activity, suitably designate assets and deal with the progression of data to and from the plan group and among any remaining gatherings (Agency, 1993). So, Construction time and delay has been a major concern to all stakeholders in the construction industry around the world because contract time overrun is a common problem that increases contractor's costs thereby reducing profit margin and reputation (Thomas Ng, Mak, Martin Skitmore, Lam, & Varnam, 2001).

Development time assessment is a vital piece of planning of an architect's gauge. Assessment of development time is significant from different angles for example for project arranging and planning, project income estimating and for proficient agreement organization. In development contracts with arrangement of rewards for project workers who finish works prior or forcing punishment for those postponing the works could be provisioned if a target strategy for count of undertaking time is accessible. The length of a development project relies basically upon the amount or size of the development work and the efficiency of the development group. Furthermore, numerous different elements may likewise influence the development length, for example, the sort of development, area and any uncommon highlights of the venture (Mishra and Aithal, 2020; Mishra and Yadav, 2019). The facts demonstrate that there is no logical strategy and booking method being applied in deciding the genuine agreement period fundamental for the finishing of the activities in different topographical areas and working conditions.

Time Cost Models in Nepal

Time cost models are not very popular in the context of Nepal specially in construction industry mainly because of the uncertainties affecting the project duration apart from the cost of project itself. The political instabilities, lack of strict adherence to contractual policies, fluctuation in

demand and supply of construction materials leads to greater uncertainties in determination of contract duration. These uncertainties leads to less scope for the time cost models. A research conducted by Mishra(2019) as part of his ph.d research finds that the most important effects of time overrun in merit were found to be Cost Overrun, Idling capital and Resources, Disputes between contracting parties, Poor quality of work, Arbitration, Negative social impact, Total abandonment, Litigation, Negative impact to other projects and Loss of labor productivity. Similar perception about the effects of time overrun was not found among the stakeholders. 3. The most important effects of cost overrun in merit were found to be Time Overrun, Supplementary agreement to cover extra cost, Delayed payment to contractors, Additional cost / Budget shortfall, Poor quality, Adversarial relations between project parties, High cost of supervision / Contact administration, Dissatisfaction by project owners / users, Lessens contribution to national economy and Negative attitude towards construction industry. Similar perception about the effects of time overrun was not found among the stakeholders. The venture time and undertaking cost of the tasks viable was discovered to be exceptionally corresponded to one another with Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient, $\rho = 0.748$. The outcome was additionally as indicated by the vast majority of the respondent's reactions. A condition, $\text{Time} = 173.29 * \text{Cost}^{0.4934}$ (time is communicated in days and cost in million NRs.) was recommended for the forecast of time and cost parts of comparative ventures. The Time Overrun and Cost Overrun of the undertakings viable was discovered to be exceptionally corresponded to one another with Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient, $\rho = 0.786$. A condition, $\text{CostOverrun} = 3.0629 * \text{Time Overrun}^{0.3081}$ (both time and cost overwhelms are communicated in rate) was recommended for the forecast of time and cost parts of comparable tasks.

A time cost model was developed by (Mishra et al. 2020) for public health buildings. Thirty five (35) public health buildings under DUDBC were analysed to determine the time-cost model. The model had the coefficient of variation (R^2) of 0.599.

Methodology

Research Design

The study was carried on the roads and bridges of Nepal. The study area is conducted based on data from various projects and divisions of Department of Road. The research is adoptive research of **Browmillow's Time Cost (BTC) Model with** Non-probability sampling method was used in this research based on accessibility of data.

Sample data consisted of data from more than 40 Road division Projects offices throughout the nation, which included data of all three major geographical regions (mountain, hill and terai).

However, only the construction contract with cost greater than 2 crore and those completed within the last five years were included for the study.

Table 1: Table of Research Matrix

SN	Objectives	Tools for Data Collection	Data Source	Analysis method	Expected outcome
1.	To generate an empirical formulae to relate the construction duration with the cost of the contract for bridge projects based on the existing data of substantially completed road projects.	Primary and secondary data, Key interview	Public entities from Division road and project offices	Quantitative Analytical Analysis	A time-costempirical relation
2.	To generate an empirical formulae to relate the construction duration with the cost of the contract for road projects based on the existing data of substantially completed road projects	Primary and secondary data, Key interview	Public entities from Division road and project offices.	Quantitative Analytical Analysis	A time-costempirical relation

The population of each roads and bridges considered for the study is presented in table 2.

Table2: Population of data:

SN	Construction Projects	Number of data:
1	Roads	78
2	Bridges	83

Setting out study alternatives

The analysis of bridges and roads was carried out as separate study namely study-1 for Estimation of contract duration for roads and study-2 for Estimation of Contract Duration for Bridges. Contract duration for Roads and Bridges depends on different factors. Hence a separate study enables to incorporate these distinctions.

Data collection

The study comprised of heterogeneous population. Due to the restricted conditions for requirement of the study (e.g. construction cost greater than 2 crore and completion of project within the last five fiscal years), and lack of ideal data management system in respective

governmental agencies, the population size itself was limited. In order to obtain as many data as possible, samples were selected on the basis of availability of data from the governmental agencies. However, from statistical point of view for regression analysis, a minimum of 10 sample size per variable has been recommended for use in regression analysis.

The data collection included sample data from more than forty Road division Projects offices throughout the nation, which included sample data of all three major geographical regions (mountain, hill and terai). However, only the construction contract with cost greater than 2 crore and those completed within the last five years were included for the study. The bridges under study were of varying length, span and type (RCC, PSC).

Secondary data

DOR databases, reports and publication and Nepal Rastra Bank (NRB) salary and wage rate index was used as secondary source of data for analysis.

Data Analysis

The data analysis was done using the graphical tool softwares. Origin was used to develop equations and prepare graphs. The raw data collected from primary and secondary sources were fine up and clustered using Ms excel. Regression analysis was used for initial development of equation using Ms excel.

Regression Analysis

Regression Analysis was carried out for data of Bridges as well as roads to project the data into linear equation.

As per the browmillow's Time cost model, the time or duration of contract is given by:-

$$T = K * C^B \quad \text{Eq (1)}$$

Taking logarithmic on both side,

$$\ln(T) = \ln(K) + B \ln(C) \quad \text{Eq (2)}$$

Where T= contract duration

B; K= constant

C= cost of contract

Also, the equation of linearity is,

$$Y = A + B * X \quad \text{Eq (3)}$$

Comparing corresponding quantities,

$$Y = \text{Ln}(T) \quad \text{Eq (4)}$$

Similarly,

$$A = \text{Ln}(K) \quad \text{Eq (5)}$$

Also,

$$X = \text{Ln}(C) \quad \text{Eq (6)}$$

Results and discussion

Application of browmilow's time-cost (BTC) model to Bridge projects

The data analysis was done using the graphical tool softwares. Origin was used to develop equations and prepare graphs. The raw data collected from primary and secondary sources were fined up and clustered using Ms excel. Regression analysis was used for initial development of equation using Ms excel.

Linear Relationship of Bridge data

The statistical parameters obtained from the data was made to fit in the linear equation using regression analysis. The mathematical procedure for separate set of data for roads and bridges is summed up below table 3-

Table3: Summary of log-log regression for Bridge data

	Intercept		Slope		Statistics
	Value	Standard Error	Value	Standard Error	Adj. R-Square
Ln Time	4.70969	0.13106	0.21527	0.01998	0.58391

$$\text{Ln}(T) = \text{Ln}(K) + B\text{Ln}(C) \quad \text{Eq (7)}$$

Comparing with $Y = A + B * X$,

$$Y = \text{Ln}(T) \quad \text{Eq (8)}$$

Similarly,

$$A = \ln(K) \tag{Eq (9)}$$

Also,

$$X = \ln(C) \tag{Eq (10)}$$

Performing regression analysis,

$$A = 4.71; \quad B = 0.215$$

BTC Model for the Bridgedata

$$K = \exp(A) = 111.018 \tag{Eq (11)}$$

Thus,

$$T = 111.018C^{0.215} \tag{Eq (12)}$$

Figure1: Linear Plot of log-log Regression for Bridge

Table 0: Actual and Predicted results for Bridge

Contract	Construction Cost (Lakhs)	Actual Duration (Days)	Predicted Duration (Days)	Prediction Error (%)
072/73-07	548.55	558	432.25	-22.54
10/2066/67	251.16	471	365.04	-22.5
BBPCU-DB-3371574-072/073-022	1629.41	697	546.21	-21.64
91.072.073	1166.02	644	508.27	-21.08
72/068-69	1204.95	640	511.84	-20.03
04/HRP/3372244/071-72 BC	592.25	549	439.22	-20
BP-DB-069/70-06	1543.29	664	539.7	-18.72
011/HRP/3372244/071-72 BC	671.88	551	451.25	-18.11
DROILAM/3371574-BP-01-072/73	311.75	462	382.61	-17.19
DROBTL/3371574/073-074/118	1174.14	606	508.78	-16.05
DRONGJ/3371574/073/74-70	1133.26	598	505.23	-15.52
DRONGJ/3371574/ 072-73/83,	1329.01	618	522.7	-15.43
DROILAM-BP-3-072/73	412.09	479	406.27	-15.19
82.068.069	673.33	524	451.7	-13.8
DRODML/337157-4/071/72/166	1375.24	611	526.37	-13.86
DROMNR/3371574/071/072-084	2618.2	698	604.87	-13.35
106.072.073	1036.33	570	495.22	-13.12
007/HRP/3372244/071-72 BC	341.44	447	389.95	-12.77
DROBTL/3371574/073-074/249	676.44	502	452.15	-9.94
025/HRP/3372244/071-72 BC	775.13	516	465.45	-9.8
75/067/68-650	218.39	392	354.25	-9.64
DRONKT/3371574/7071/129	2312	649	588.75	-9.29
DROMNR/3371574/073/074-004	468.84	460	417.8	-9.18
DROMNR/3373204/073/074-098	431.09	448	410.35	-8.41
DRODMK/3371574/072/73-050	263.78	403	369.08	-8.42
105.072.073	699.34	497	455.32	-8.39
PCU-DB-PQ-CR 071/72-23	12435.17	911	845.57	-7.19
HRP/3372244/073-74/BC-035	488.06	448	421.16	-6

NSKRP/337145-4/09/073/074	567.7	460	435.29	-5.38
DROBTL/3371574/073-074/086	603.42	463	440.99	-4.76
DRODMK/3371574/072/73-027	299.77	398	379.18	-4.73
HRP/3372244/072/73 BC-044	540.99	447	430.96	-3.59
DROMNR/3371574/073/074-166	333.09	402	388	-3.49
DROBTL/3371574/073-074/319	904.71	497	481.07	-3.21
DROMNR/3371574/073/074-100	310.88	391	382.23	-2.25
DROMNR/3371574/073/074-101	588.34	448	438.79	-2.06
DROBTL/3371574/073-074/366	683.39	458	453.05	-1.09
KCRP/337145-4/01/073/074	692.34	459	454.42	-1
92.072.073	700.56	459	455.32	-0.81
DROLHN/337157-4/072/073-86	645.45	447	447.2	0.05
DROBTL/3371574/073-074/117 (re)	454.74	413	414.89	0.46
DROMNR/3371574/073/074-084	477.49	417	419.48	0.6
DROTLR/337157/073/74-03	597.05	436	440.1	0.95
DROBTL/3371574/073-074/329	763.52	458	464.06	1.33
DROMNR/3371574/073/074-174	717.82	449	457.61	1.92
DROBTL/3371574/073-074/326	551.51	423	432.69	2.3
58-73/74	446.64	403	413.23	2.54
CDRO7/650/066/67-111	248.34	353	364.31	3.21
HRP/3372244/072/73 BC-043	757.9	447	463.13	3.61
TSPRP/3371574/073/74-186	420.83	393	407.9	3.8
NSKRP/337320-4/11/073/074	369.61	382	396.63	3.83
DROMNR/3371574/073/074-175	792.83	449	467.79	4.19
DROMNR/3371574/073/074-085	473.33	398	418.64	5.19
DROMNR/3371574/073/074-168	534.35	403	429.67	6.62
DROBTL/3371574/073-074/250	658.86	420	449.44	7.01
DROMNR/3371574/073/074-103	435.86	381	411.17	7.92
DROSKT/3371574/073/74-105	432.42	380	410.35	7.99
DROMNR/3371574/073/074-173	438.65	381	411.58	8.03
BP-DB-650/070/71-04	1398.96	483	528.48	9.42

DROBTL/3371574/073-074/328	594.03	400	439.66	9.92
PCU-DB-CR-071/72-17	1440.24	483	531.66	10.08
HRP/3372244/073-74/BC-030	324.82	346	386.07	11.59
DRODML/3371574/73/74-141	2109.74	517	577.67	11.74
BBPCU-DB-3371574-071/072-019	1560.43	483	540.78	11.97
TSPRP/3371574/073/74-179	654.99	398	448.99	12.82
DRODML/3373204/72/73-85	297.51	334	378.8	13.42
DRODML/3373204/72/73-84	298.46	334	378.8	13.42
DRONKT/3373204/7475/009	449.6	362	414.06	14.39
MIDHLKTM/3371384/2073/074-203	363.99	345	395.45	14.63
073/74-166	253.36	319	365.77	14.67
DROBTL/3371574/073-074/083	383.33	347	399.82	15.23
DROLHN/337157-4/072/073-08	301.42	329	379.94	15.49
BBPCU - 3371574-DB-072/73-025	1300.53	435	520.09	19.57
DROILAM/3373204/074/75-14	340.27	322	389.95	21.11
BBPCU-DB-072/73-015	5730.82	591	716.23	21.19
MIDHLKTM/3371384/2073/074/201	477.25	345	419.48	21.59
DROMNR/3371574/073/074-006	413.41	333	406.67	22.13
DROCHT/3371574/073/74-182	766.09	377	464.06	23.1
DROILAM/3371574/074/75-12	395.07	322	402.63	25.05
DROMNR/3371574/073/074-005	468.85	334	417.8	25.09
BP/DB /070/71-03	2220.42	460	583.48	26.85
BBPCU-DB-072/73-015	7139.28	591	750.7	27.03
BBPCU- 3371574-DB- 072/73-021	2209.9	440	582.9	32.48

Table5: Summary of model predictive errors for Bridge

Maximum error (%)	Minimum Error (%)	Average Error (%)
32.48	-22.54	1.036%

Application of browmilow's time-cost (BTC) model to Roadprojects .

Linear Relationship of Road data

Performing regression analysis as above,

$$A = 4.5270; \quad B = 0.2159$$

BTC Model for the Road Data

$$K = \exp(A) = 92.482 \quad \text{Eq (13)}$$

So,

$$T = 92.482C^{0.2159} \quad \text{Eq (14)}$$

Table6: Summary of log-log regression for Road data

	Intercept		Slope		Statistics
	Value	Standard Error	Value	Standard Error	Adj. R-Square
Ln Time	4.52701	0.1759	0.21593	0.02327	0.52503

Figure 1: Linear Plot of log-log Regression for Road

Table7: Actual and Predicted results for Road

Contract	Construction Cost (Lakhs)	Actual Duration (Days)	Predicted Duration (Days)	Prediction Error (%)
ACQMP/TRIP/RBID/02/2069/071	3522.642322	843	539.42	-36.02
003/HRP/3372244/071-72 BC	354.5163323	512	328.55	-35.84
ACQMP/TRIP/RBID/01/2069/070	3735.394223	795	546.29	-31.29
92-72/73	1730.442867	662	462.67	-30.12
KVRIP/3371494/073/74/008	3421.230828	761	536.03	-29.57
TCRP/3371104/072/073-003	873.6735986	564	399.19	-29.23
190.071.072	1297.339472	588	434.76	-26.07
MIDHLDNG/B-01/067/68	897.5895069	536	401.52	-25.09
MIDHLDNG/B-01/067/68	897.5895069	536	401.52	-25.09
MIDHLKTM/3371384/2072/073-007	728.3283914	506	383.81	-24.15
MIDHLKTM/3371384/2073/074-006	318.7165787	423	321.08	-24.1
DROTLR/337165/2072/73-33	1927.146955	617	473.55	-23.25
001/02-202	460.972399	449	347.71	-22.56
MIDHLDNG/3371384-072/073-014	4048.949039	717	555.88	-22.48
DRODMK/3371234/073/74-25	833.8113285	489	395.18	-19.19
RIP/337133/BD-08/2071-072	3039.946314	638	522.52	-18.11
DROBTL/3373664/073-074/283	1927.544792	577	473.57	-17.93
DRODMK/3371234/072/73-123	473.1099778	415	349.67	-15.75
5/067-68	471.5300663	414	349.42	-15.6
MIDHLDNG/3371384-072/73-001	4403.442373	663	566.05	-14.63
TRIP/337312/BB/071/72-05	6070.596332	706	606.68	-14.07
018/HRP/3372244/071-72 BC	3982.471687	641	553.9	-13.59
DRONTK/3371234/7172/107	2091.25265	553	481.98	-12.85
HRP/3372244/072-073/UR-008	2834.754024	586	514.7	-12.17
DROTLR/337165/2072/73-34	2708.78372	570	509.67	-10.59
TRIP/337312/BB/071/72-03	7148.999424	702	628.49	-10.48

Contract	Construction Cost (Lakhs)	Actual Duration (Days)	Predicted Duration (Days)	Prediction Error (%)
RIP/337133/JPR-13/2070-073	3562.563906	596	540.73	-9.28
3373124/TRIP/JJ/071-72/01	5558.852208	655	595.26	-9.13
MIDHLDNG/072/073/-012	4153.949693	615	558.96	-9.12
MIDHLDNG/072/073/-012	4153.949693	615	558.96	-9.12
RIP/337133/JPR-12/2070-072	4161.487585	615	559.18	-9.08
TRIP/337312/RBID2070/071-01	4893.814916	630	579.1	-8.08
DROCHT/3373294/071/72/102	522.3259312	388	357.22	-7.94
3373124/TRIP/JJ/071-72/02	6149.172906	647	608.37	-5.98
DROMNR/3373664/073/074-155	790.2868858	415	390.64	-5.87
DROMNR/3371304/073/074-020	2691.074273	535	508.95	-4.87
DROMNR/3373594/071/072-065	434.7728491	353	343.35	-2.74
DROBTL/3073664/074-75/021	813.237228	394	393.06	-0.24
104.072.073	573.1049405	364	364.45	0.13
3373664-243/2073/74	2093.528529	479	482.09	0.65
072/073-01	987.7862667	406	409.91	0.97
MIDHLKTM/3371384/2071/072-202	3752.855123	538	546.84	1.65
DROMNR/3373664/073/074-156	1352.181021	427	438.67	2.74
DROMNR/3373664/074/075-015	392.668533	322	335.88	4.32
KVRIP/3371494/071/72/037	9452.705911	639	667.56	4.47
TRIP/337312/RBID2071/072-01	8398.36581	616	650.73	5.64
NSKRP/3371454/ 072/073-06	5823.619196	565	601.27	6.42
MIDHLDNG/070/071/032	2999.246097	488	521	6.77
MIDHLDNG/070/071/032	2999.246097	488	521	6.77
DROMNR/3373664/073/074-163	454.958046	320	346.73	8.36
DROBHT/3373564/071/72-134 re	2442.686401	459	498.42	8.59
DROMNR/3373664/073/074-160	1783.107093	427	465.67	9.06
DROSKT/337333-4/074/75-23	1799.792759	427	466.61	9.28

Contract	Construction Cost (Lakhs)	Actual Duration (Days)	Predicted Duration (Days)	Prediction Error (%)
KVRIP/3371494/071/72/038	7566.706292	577	636.24	10.27
HRP/3372244/072-73/UR003	5208.167331	531	586.94	10.54
121/072/073	1679.332495	403	459.68	14.07
DROHKR/3371234/071/72-056	318.3226981	273	321	17.59
DROLTP/3371494/072/73-110	287.444358	260	314	20.77
HRP/3372244/072-073/UR-009	3036.730783	426	522.4	22.63
KVRIP/3371494/071/72/039	9002.783243	535	660.57	23.48
DROBHT/3371234 /071/072- 203	455.6736302	277	346.85	25.22
DROMNR/3373664/074/075-014	765.244035	306	387.93	26.78
DROBHT/3371234 /071/072-202	347.8773883	255	327.21	28.32
RSDPAFII-DOR-W-BNC-NCB-4	3498.652484	419	538.62	28.55
KVRIP/3371494/071/72/040	11460.88032	540	695.91	28.88
TCRP/3371104/074/075-001	788.296851	302	390.42	29.28
MIDHLDNG/073/074/-002	390.13587	254	335.41	32.06
MIDHLDNG/073/074/-002	390.13587	254	335.41	32.06
DRODML/337165-3/072/73-079	309.0491933	241	318.95	32.35
SRCP/ICB/LB-01	12327.64431	524	706.95	34.92
MIDHLKTM/3371384/2073/074-005	3834.447509	406	549.39	35.32
MIDHLDNG/070/071/-030	3943.282855	406	552.72	36.14
MIDHLDNG/070/071/-030	3943.282855	406	552.72	36.14
NSKRP/3371454/ 070/071-20	7350.912679	463	632.28	36.57
DROBHT/3371234 /071/072- 200	512.2453114	256	355.72	38.96
DROILAM-PM-13-073/74	413.6822681	242	339.68	40.37
MIDHLKTM/3371384/2074/75-003	11579.82764	464	697.47	50.32
MHH/ES-BH/1-09/068/69	357.8268375	194	329.21	69.7

Table8: Summary of model predictive errors fo Road

Maximum error (%)	Minimum Error (%)	Average Error (%)
69.7%	-35.84%	2.510769%

Interpretation of Time-Cost Model.

The equation for determination of contract duration obtained from the data studied for roads and bridges are as follows:-

For Bridges:-

$$T = 111.018C^{0.215} \quad \text{Eq (15)}$$

Table9: Summary of log-log regression for Bridge data:

	Intercept		Slope		Statistics
	Value	Standard Error	Value	Standard Error	Adj. R-Square
Ln Time	4.70969	0.13106	0.21527	0.01998	0.58391

There is no particular limiting value of (R²) on the basis of which the model can be judged. Higher value of (R²) indicates better predictability of the model. However, the value of (R²) in the range of 0.4 to 0.6 is considered to be acceptable in simple as well as multiple linear regression. Also **Error! Reference source not found.** has been added for illustrated R² of BTC in various projects.

Table 0-1: Summary of log-log regression for Road data:

	Intercept		Slope		Statistics
	Value	Standard Error	Value	Standard Error	Adj. R-Square
Ln Time	4.52701	0.1759	0.21593	0.02327	0.52503

For Bridges, the coefficient of determination (R²) is 0.58391 that is 58.39% . This implies that only 58.39% of variability in the data is incorporated by this equation. The intercept value of 4.70969 gives the value of constant K in the equation which is 111.018. This value of K represents that as per the given equation, 111.018 days are required for completion of work worth contract amount of 1 lakhs. However, this statement cannot be generalized as the model is made to suite only for amount greater than 2 crores.

The slope intercept value of 0.21527 indicates the influence of size of project(measured by its cost) on the contract duration. Larger the value of slope intercept, larger is the influence of project size on the duration.

For Roads:-

$$T = 92.482C^{0.2159} \quad \text{Eq (16)}$$

For Roads, the coefficient of determination (R^2) is 0.52503 that is 52.50% . This implies that only 52.50% of variability in the data is incorporated by this equation. The intercept value of 4.52701 gives the value of constant K in the equation which is 92.482. This value of K represents that as per the given equation, 92.482 days are required for completion of work worth contract amount of 1 lakhs. However, this statement cannot be generalized as the model is made to suite only for amount greater than 2 crores.

The slope intercept value of 0.21593 indicates the influence of size of project(measured by its cost) on the contract duration. Larger the value of slope intercept, larger is the influence of project size on the duration.

Comparing the equation of Roads and bridges, the value of K is larger for bridges and roads projects have a greater value of slope intercept with slight difference than that of bridges.

Time-Cost Model for roads and projects of specific geographical area of Butwal, Rupandehi

To analyse the applicability of Browmillo's time cost model for a specific geographical area with less number of data, the regression analysis was repeated only for the data of road and bridge project under Butwal Division.

Linear Relationship of Bridge data for Butwal only

Number of data obtained for bridges in butwal= 20

A= 3.00912; B=0.48861

Table 2: Summary of log-log regression for Bridge data

	Intercept		Slope		Statistics
	Value	Standard Error	Value	Standard Error	Adj. R-Square
Ln Time	3.00912	0.53835	0.48861	0.08172	0.64649

BTC Model for the Butwal Bridge data

$$K = \exp(A) = 20.269 \quad \text{Eq (17)}$$

Thus,

$$T = 20.269C^{0.48861} \quad \text{Eq (18)}$$

Table 3: Linear Plot of log-log Regression for Bridges in Butwal

Linear Relationship of Road data for Butwal only

Number of data obtained for roads in butwal= 8

A= 4.12348; B=0.29385

Table 4: Summary of log-log regression for Bridge data.

Table 0-5 Summary of log-log regression for Bridge data

	Intercept		Slope		Statistics
	Value	Standard Error	Value	Standard Error	Adj. R-Square
Ln Time	4.12348	0.50951	0.29385	0.06558	0.73155

BTC Model for the Butwal Road data

$$K = \exp(A) = 61.774 \quad \text{Eq (1)}$$

Thus,

$$T = 61.774C^{0.29385} \quad \text{Eq (2)}$$

Figure 0-2: Linear Plot of log-log Regression for Roads in Butwal

Conclusions

Following equations were obtained from the research work as regards to objective 1 and 2:-

For Bridges:-

$$T = 111.018C^{0.215} \quad \text{Eq (3)}$$

For Roads:-

$$T = 92.482C^{0.2159} \quad \text{Eq (4)}$$

Where, T= duration of work in days;

C= Cost of the project measured in lakhs.

Time cost model is a simple yet effective way to deal with the uncertainties that comes in the procurement processes in the estimation of construction duration. This model can easily be reconstructed with new datas along the span of time. With changes in technologies and work culture, the time required for the prediction of construction duration also changes. With this model, and with proper data on construction duration and cost, the time cost model can be regenerated. In this thesis, Browmillo's model is an ineffective instrument for the purpose of estimation of time cost model. The rate of increase in the construction time decreases with the increase in cost that is due to the non linearity of the equation. The time cost relation presented above is in regard of the working days required for the completion of certain works. Conversion of working days into the calender days can be carried out as per the individual requirements and project complexities. A sample of the conversion methodology for the roads and bridges projects in Nepal has been presented as recommendation.

References

1. Agency, C. I. D. (1993). A report on the time and cost performance of Australian building projects completed 1988–1993. In: Construction Industry Development Agency and Master Builders Australia Sydney.

2. Bayram, S. (2017). Duration prediction models for construction projects: In terms of cost or physical characteristics? *KSCE Journal of Civil Engineering*, 21(6), 2049-2060.
3. Bayram, S., & Al-Jibouri, S. (2018). Reference Class Forecasting Method in Predicting Construction Project Duration. *Journal of Natural & Applied Sciences*, 22(3).
4. Bromilow, F. (1969). Contract time performance expectations and the reality. Paper presented at the Building forum.
5. Bromilow, F., & Henderson, J. (1977). Procedures for reckoning and valuing the performance of building contracts: Division of Building Research, CSIRO.
6. Bromilow, F., Hinds, M., & Moody, N. (1980). AIQS survey of building contract time performance. *The Building Economist*, 19(2), 79-82.
7. Bromilow, F., Hinds, M., & Moody, N. (1988). The time and cost performance of building contracts 1976-1986: Australasian Institute of Quantity Surveyors.
8. DOR, (2014). Construction time for Road and Bridge works
9. Ghimire, S. & Mishra, A. K. (2019). Comparative Study of Prospective Delay Analysis Techniques (DATs). *Saudi J Civ Eng.*, 3(5), 84-95. DOI:10.21276/sjce.2019.3.5.1.
10. Haque, K. M., Hasin, M., & Akhtar, A. (2012). Genetic algorithm for project time-cost optimization in fuzzy environment. *Journal of Industrial Engineering and Management (JIEM)*, 5(2), 364-381.
11. Mishra, Anjay & J.S, Sudarsan & Nithiyantham, S.. (2020). Assessment of time–cost model of public health buildings in Nepal. *Asian Journal of Civil Engineering*.
12. Mishra, A.K., (2019). Assessment of project performance in terms of time cost and quality. PhD thesis Institute of Business Management, Chhatrapati Shahu Ji Maharaj University Kanpur, India.
Mishra A.K., & Aithal, P. S. (2020). Financial Impact Assessment of Time Overrun: A Case of Second Small Towns Water Supply and Sanitation Sector Project, Nepal *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)*, 4(2), 159-173. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4074715>
13. Yadav, S. K., & Mishra, A. K. (2019). Status of Time and Cost Overrun of Health Building Construction Projects in Nepal. *Sch J Eng Tech*, 7(9), 262- 270. DOI: 10.36347/SJET.2019.v07i09.003.